

IMPACT OF MODE SHAPE AND ACOUSTIC GUST ON BLADE FLUTTER STABILITY

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ABSTRACT

Recent studies have shown that flutter of rotor blades in aero-engine can occur in the absence of flow separation. Two key parameters have been shown to be highly influential in determining the flutter stability of such blades: mode shape and acoustic reflection. As turbomachinery blade aerofoils are thinned to improve performance and reduce weight, flutter dependency in those aspects are likely to remain as key aeroelastic challenges in designing a flutter-free machine. Therefore, this paper investigates the flutter mechanism of blade vibration, driven by mode shape and incoming acoustic gust, using an aerodynamically simple yet informative model. It is shown, by conducting aerodynamic work sum analysis, that a stable blade can flutter as a result of interaction between mode shape and incoming acoustic gust.

INTRODUCTION

Stall flutter is one of the most common types of flutter in turbomachinery. When a rotor operates near the stall line, shock wave movement, boundary layer separation and radial flow migration on the suction surface can contribute to large amplitude oscillatory forces and interacts with the blade to cause flutter [1].

Recent studies have shown that flutter of rotor blades in aero-engine can however occur in the absence of flow separation [2–4]. In those cases, as the rotor is throttled, the onset of flutter, instead of stall and surge, forms the limiting operating condition. Two key parameters have been shown to be highly in-

fluential in determining the flutter stability of such blades: mode shape and acoustic reflection. It has been shown that the amount of twist component in the 1st flapwise bending (1F) mode can result in significant changes in the aero-damping of fan blades [2, 4]. Acoustic reflection from bladed structures, ducting and intake have also been shown to be instrumental for flutter of blade rows in embedded environment [3]. Despite the efforts of computational modelling using CFD, improvement in fundamental understanding of such flutter mechanism is still been sought.

The objective of this paper is to investigate and demonstrate the flutter mechanism of blade vibration, driven by mode shape and incoming acoustic gust, using an aerodynamically simple yet informative model. To achieve this goal, aerodynamic work sum analysis is carried out to evaluate the contributions of blade damping from various unsteady sources. The study focus on the vibration of a thin annulus blade row consisted of flat plates inside a long straight duct immersed in uniform inviscid flow. By doing so, the flow and vibration motion of blades can be approximated as two-dimensional, whereby the effect of mode shape can be conveniently decoupled and analysed from other effects such as three-dimensional flow migration and viscous forces. Moreover, for the sake of clarity - without too much loss in generality, results for the 0° inter-blade phase angle mode are presented in this paper. This allows investigation of the interaction between blade vibration and duct acoustics, while being free from the influence of passage volume change. It is of the author's experience that most of the observations in this paper are likely to hold true for modes with non-zero inter-blade phase angles [5]. Despite the use of a simple model, it can be shown that the observed

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FIGURE 1: Computation domain.

FIGURE 2: Mid-layer mesh in blade-to-blade plane.

trends and conclusions in this work are valid for common turbomachinery blades [3, 4, 6, 7]. The study in this paper will show, in a straightforward and easily comprehensible form, that a flat plate in two-dimensional uniform flow can flutter as a result of mode shape and incoming gust interaction.

COMPUTATIONAL MODEL

The computation domain consists of a thin annulus blade row inside a long straight duct. The blades are made of thin flat plates and have identical sections all radial heights, and are connected to the duct walls at the hub and casing surfaces without clearances. The hub/tip ratio is approximately 0.965. The inflow and outflow boundaries of the duct are placed approximately 10 chords away from the blades. Figure 1 illustrates the outline of the computation domain. For all the computations performed in this work, a single passage domain representing a 1/45th sector is used.

The grid used for blading is semi-structured [8]. The passage mesh is resolved using approximately 120,000 grid points with 5 radial mesh layers. Figure 2 shows the mid-layer mesh in the blade-to-blade plane. In order to accurately resolve the

FIGURE 3: Schematic illustration for a pure plunge mode (left) and a pure twist mode about mid-chord (right).

propagation of acoustic waves, approximately 150 mesh points are used for the shortest axial wavelength expected.

All the computations are performed as inviscid and in a single passage fashion with periodic boundary conditions at the blade-to-blade boundaries [9]. The steady state flow solutions are obtained by imposing total pressure, total temperature and flow angle at the far-field inflow boundary and static pressure at the outflow boundary. The incident flow angle is maintained at 0° throughout this study, so that the mean aerodynamic loading of the blade is zero. For unsteady computations, these boundaries are treated using non-reflecting boundary conditions to minimise numerical reflection.

For aeroelastic computations, blade vibration is prescribed in the mode of interest. The pure plunge mode and the pure twist mode studied in this work are illustrated schematically in Figure 3. Throughout the work the flow Mach number is fixed at 0.3 and the reduced frequency is varied through vibration frequency. Aerodynamic damping is calculated from the aerodynamic work sum per cycle based on a fully developed periodic flow solution. The physical time step for flutter computations is resolved as 200 time steps per vibration cycle. This time step is chosen based on a temporal convergence study.

For all the cases studied, the plunge vibration is started with a constant initial translational velocity of v_{0p} perpendicular to the chord line (in the positive circumferential direction). For the twist mode, the centre of rotation is the mid-chord of the blade, and the motion is started with a constant initial tangential velocity of v_{0t} at the leading edge (in the sense of increasing stagger angle and closing the blade).

The plunge motion of the flat plate can be expressed as

$$\dot{h}_p(t) = v_{0p} e^{-i\omega t} \quad (1)$$

$$h_p(t) = -\frac{v_{0p}}{i\omega} e^{-i\omega t} \quad (2)$$

where $h_p(t)$ is the displacement of the plunge motion perpendicular to the chord and $\dot{h}_p(t)$ is the translational velocity of the blade.

The twist motion can be expressed as

$$\dot{\theta}_T(t) = \frac{2v_{0T}}{c} e^{-i\omega t} \quad (3)$$

$$\theta_T(t) = -\frac{2v_{0T}}{i\omega c} e^{-i\omega t} \quad (4)$$

where c is the chord length, $\theta_T(t)$ is the rotation of the blade about mid-chord and $\dot{\theta}_T(t)$ is the angular velocity of the blade.

For most of the cases computed in this work (unless otherwise specified), the initial velocity v_0 is kept constant at a Mach number of 0.0035 for both the plunge and twist modes. As a consequence, the maximum displacement decreases with the increase in frequency. For a given frequency, the maximum displacement at the blade leading edge is roughly the same for the plunge mode and the twist mode. The prescribed blade motion is large enough to be well outside the numerical ‘noise’, but small enough for the unsteady flow to be well represented as linear. The resultant displacements at the leading and trailing edges are less than 0.3% of the blade chord.

AERO-DAMPING EVALUATION BASED ON THE ENERGY METHOD

Flutter stability of the blade is assessed using an energy method based on the work sum of aerodynamic loading. The aerodynamic work per vibration cycle, w , is computed using

$$w = \int_T \oint pn \cdot \mathbf{v} dS dt \quad (5)$$

where t denotes time, T is the period of vibration, pn is the local aerodynamic force vector, \mathbf{v} is the local blade velocity vector and $\oint dS$ denotes the contour integral over the blade surface. In the absence of mechanical damping, positive aerodynamic work corresponds to a net energy transfer from the surrounding flow to the blade vibration, hence indicates flutter instability. On the contrary, negative work done leads to positive damping and stable blade.

Aerodynamic damping can be computed from the aerodynamic work per cycle using

$$\zeta = -\frac{w}{v_0^2} \quad (6)$$

It will be shown in the following analyses that the energy method is a useful tool for studying the interaction between mode shape, acoustic wave and blade flutter stability. It is worth noting that the aim of this work is to investigate the onset of flutter, and not limit cycle vibrations, thus the use of the energy method is sufficient.

FIGURE 4: Aero-damping variation with stagger angle θ , and vibration motion.

EFFECT OF MODE SHAPE

In the first step, aeroelastic computations are carried out, in the pure plunge mode and the pure twist mode respectively, for different blade stagger angles and reduced frequencies. Figure 4 shows the computed blade aero-damping as a function of reduced frequency for different blade stagger angles. It can be seen from the plot that aero-damping is positive for all the cases studied. Moreover, aero-damping is seen to be largely independent of stagger angle, which is a result of zero passage volume change resulting from the 0° inter-blade phase angle boundary condition. Overall, the blade aero-damping shows a decrease as reduced frequency increases. The damping value tends to zero when the vibration frequency tends to infinity as the blade becomes too stiff to be affected by the flow.

Interestingly, the results shown in Figure 4 indicate that aero-damping for the pure twist mode remains nearly zero for all the stagger angles and reduced frequencies studied, and is an order of magnitude smaller than that for the pure plunge mode. This begs the question of whether the twist motion plays an important part in the flutter of turbomachinery blades, and how blade aero-damping is influenced by the twist component in its mode shape. With the currently knowledge of turbomachinery aeroelasticity, it is known and widely acknowledged that twist motion can be highly influential in determining flutter stability of blades. However, its impact on flutter stability is usually convoluted and a straightforward understanding is usually difficult to achieve. Hence, the rest of this section will try to highlight the impact of mode shape on blade flutter stability, in a simple and easily comprehensible fashion, using a work sum analysis. It will be shown that a stable blade can flutter with a simple and small tweak in its twist mode shape components.

FIGURE 5: Instantaneous unsteady pressure contour for a pure plunge mode (top) and a pure twist mode about mid-chord (bottom).

Work sum analysis

In order to understand the effect of mode shape on blade aero-damping, an analysis of aerodynamic work contribution is carried out using the energy method by calculating aerodynamic work per vibration cycle based on Equation 5.

Consider a blade vibrating in the pure plunge mode, the aerodynamic work per cycle can be calculated based on the local unsteady loading vector induced by the plunge motion $p_p \mathbf{n}$ and the local blade velocity vector due to plunge motion \mathbf{v}_p as

$$w_{pp} = \int_T \oint p_p \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{v}_p dS dt \quad (7)$$

where subscript P denotes variables associated with the plunge motion.

Equation 7 evaluates the aerodynamic work for a blade vibrating in the pure plunge mode, due to unsteady loading induced by the plunge motion (by perturbing the surrounding flow field), hence the notation w_{pp} . It should be noted that, throughout this work, the subscripts are arranged so that the first letter denotes the source of unsteady loading (induced by either the plunge or twist motion), and the second letter denotes which mode the loading is applied to.

Similarly, the aerodynamic work per cycle for a blade vibrating in the twist mode, due to unsteady loading induced by the twist motion, can be expressed as

$$w_{TT} = \int_T \oint p_T \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{v}_T dS dt \quad (8)$$

where subscript T denotes variables associated with the twist motion.

It is worth noting that the perturbed pressure field p_p and p_T induce unsteady loading in terms of both lift and moment. This is illustrated by the instantaneous unsteady pressure contours shown in Figure 5. However, the integral of unsteady moment about mid-chord induced by p_p and the pure plunge motion \mathbf{v}_p results in nearly zero contribution to aerodynamic work

FIGURE 6: Decomposition of a two-dimensional flap mode into a linear superposition of a pure plunge mode and a pure twist mode about mid-chord.

w_{pp} . Similarly, the integral of unsteady lift induced by p_T and the twist motion \mathbf{v}_T results in nearly zero contribution to aerodynamic work w_{TT} .

The aerodynamic damping for blade vibrating in these two modes can be expressed as

$$\zeta_{pp} = -\frac{w_{pp}}{v_{0p}^2} \quad (9)$$

$$\zeta_{TT} = -\frac{w_{TT}}{v_{0T}^2} \quad (10)$$

where v_{0p} and v_{0T} are the initial velocities for the plunge mode and the twist mode respectively. Positive damping denotes stable blade and negative damping indicates flutter. The aero-damping shown in Figure 4 can be attributed to ζ_{pp} and ζ_{TT} for the pure plunge mode and the pure twist mode respectively.

Aero-damping for a flap mode

Blades, or blade sections, in turbomachineries rarely vibrate in a pure plunge mode or a pure twist mode, due to their complex three dimensional geometry, non-uniform structural properties and the mechanism of mounting. Instead, the mode shape for such a blade usually consists of a combination of plunge and twist components. It was shown in [6] that the 1F mode for typical rotor blades, which is usually the most susceptible to flutter, can be approximated as a linear superposition of a pure plunge component and a pure twist component about mid-chord. The decomposition of such a mixed mode (will be referred to as the flap mode in the rest of this paper) is illustrated in Figure 6. It is worth noting that flap modes of this type are equivalent to pure twist modes with centre of rotation downstream of mid-chord (usually aft of the trailing edge).

For small amplitude blade vibration in the flap mode, the instantaneous local velocity vector \mathbf{v} on the blade surface can be expressed as a linear superposition of contributions due to a pure plunge motion and a pure twist motion about mid-chord, i.e.

$$\mathbf{v}_F = (1 - \gamma)\mathbf{v}_p + \gamma\mathbf{v}_T \quad (11)$$

where subscript F denotes variables associated with the flap mode and γ represents the contribution of twist component in

the flap mode subjected to $0 \leq \gamma \leq 1$. The value of γ is 0 for a pure plunge mode and 1 for a pure twist mode.

Similarly, within the realm of linear perturbation, the perturbed pressure field p can be expressed as a superposition of the plunge and the twist induced disturbances, which is

$$p_F = (1 - \gamma)p_p + \gamma p_t \quad (12)$$

Hence the aerodynamic work for a blade vibrating in the flap mode can be obtained using

$$w_{FF} = \int_T \oint ((1 - \gamma)p_p + \gamma p_t) \mathbf{n} \cdot ((1 - \gamma)\mathbf{v}_p + \gamma \mathbf{v}_t) dS dt \quad (13)$$

The above equation can be expanded and grouped into four distinct terms as follows

$$w_{FF} = w_{PP} + w_{PT} + w_{TP} + w_{TT} \quad (14)$$

where

$$w_{PP} = (1 - \gamma)^2 \int_T \oint p_p \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{v}_p dS dt \quad (15)$$

$$w_{PT} = \gamma(1 - \gamma) \int_T \oint p_p \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{v}_t dS dt \quad (16)$$

$$w_{TP} = \gamma(1 - \gamma) \int_T \oint p_t \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{v}_p dS dt \quad (17)$$

$$w_{TT} = \gamma^2 \int_T \oint p_t \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{v}_t dS dt \quad (18)$$

It is interesting to see that besides the previously identified terms w_{PP} and w_{TT} , two new terms emerge: w_{PT} which represents the aerodynamic work for the twist mode component due to unsteady loading induced by the plunge motion, and conversely w_{TP} represents the aerodynamic work for the plunge mode component due to unsteady moment induced by the twist motion. These two terms represent the coupling effect between the plunge and the twist components in a flap mode, where energy is transferred between the two vibration motions through the medium of flow. It will be shown that these coupling terms are indeed responsible for blade flutter in the first flap mode.

Based on the aerodynamic work sum, the blade aero-damping can be calculated using

$$\zeta_{PP} = -\frac{w_{PP}}{(1 - \gamma)^2 v_{0p}^2} \quad (19)$$

$$\zeta_{PT} = -\frac{w_{PT}}{\gamma^2 v_{0t}^2} \quad (20)$$

$$\zeta_{TP} = -\frac{w_{TP}}{(1 - \gamma)^2 v_{0p}^2} \quad (21)$$

$$\zeta_{TT} = -\frac{w_{TT}}{\gamma^2 v_{0t}^2} \quad (22)$$

which, combined with Equations 15 to 18, yield

$$\zeta_{PP} = -\frac{1}{v_{0p}^2} \int_T \oint p_p \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{v}_p dS dt \quad (23)$$

$$\zeta_{PT} = -\frac{1 - \gamma}{\gamma} \frac{1}{v_{0t}^2} \int_T \oint p_p \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{v}_t dS dt \quad (24)$$

$$\zeta_{TP} = -\frac{\gamma}{1 - \gamma} \frac{1}{v_{0p}^2} \int_T \oint p_t \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{v}_p dS dt \quad (25)$$

$$\zeta_{TT} = -\frac{1}{v_{0t}^2} \int_T \oint p_t \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{v}_t dS dt \quad (26)$$

and the aero-damping for the flap mode can be expressed as

$$\zeta_{FF} = \zeta_{PP} + \zeta_{PT} + \zeta_{TP} + \zeta_{TT} \quad (27)$$

It will be shown that the decomposition and grouping of the aero-damping provides a convenient way of analysing and understanding the effect of mode shape. Moreover, Equations 19 to 26 are valid when γ is neither 0 or 1. For a pure plunge mode ($\gamma = 0$), the aero-work contributions ζ_{PT} , ζ_{TP} and ζ_{TT} are all zero, and so are their respective damping contributions. Similarly for a pure twist mode the only non-zero contribution is ζ_{TT} .

The physical meaning of the four damping values in Equations 19 to 22 can be expressed as follows:

1. The aerodynamic work for the plunge mode component is driven by the unsteady lift on the blade surface, whereby energy transfer takes place by displacing the blade in the direction normal to the chord line. Since unsteady lift can be induced by either the plunge or the twist motion, it is natural to split the aero-work contributions for the plunge mode into two groups: w_{PP} for plunge motion induced lift and w_{TP} for twist motion induced lift.
2. The aerodynamic work for the twist mode component is driven by the unsteady moment on the blade surface, whereby energy transfer takes place by rotating the blade about the mid-chord. Hence the aero-work contributions for the twist mode can be grouped into w_{PT} for plunge motion induced moment and w_{TT} for twist motion induced moment.

It is important to note that, as can be seen in Equations 23 to 26, the amount of twist in a flap mode affects blade aero-damping through only the 'cross product' terms, namely ζ_{PT} and ζ_{TP} . With the increase of twist component (increasing γ), the aero-damping contribution ζ_{TP} increases in magnitude, and the aero-damping contribution ζ_{PT} sees a decrease.

Based on the analysis above, the aforementioned four blade aero-damping contributions, namely ζ_{PP} , ζ_{PT} , ζ_{TP} and ζ_{TT} , are calculated for the cases studied. The aerodynamic work contributions w_{PP} and w_{TT} were obtained directly from the two sets of unsteady CFD solutions, computed using the pure plunge mode

FIGURE 7: Aerodynamic damping contributions due to plunge and twist motions, $\theta_s = 45^\circ$, $\gamma = 0.5$.

and the pure twist mode respectively (cases presented in Figure 4). The aerodynamic work contributions w_{PT} and w_{TP} were obtained, without the need of further CFD computations, using Equations 16 and 17 through post-processing of the two aforementioned sets of solutions.

The computed blade aero-damping contributions for a flap mode with $\gamma = 0.5$ are plotted in Figure 7 as a function of reduced frequency. It can be seen from the plot that the aero-damping ζ_{PT} and ζ_{TT} for the twist mode component (unsteady moment driven) are small compared with the aero-damping ζ_{PP} and ζ_{TP} for the plunge mode component (unsteady lift driven). This can be inferred from Figure 5, where it can be seen that the unsteady moment induced by both the plunge and twist motions is small compared with the induced unsteady lift, since the unsteady moment generated at the front half of the blade is largely cancelled out by that at the rear half. Moreover, it can be seen from Figure 7 that, aero-damping for the plunge mode component driven by plunge motion induced perturbations (ζ_{PP}) is always positive, and the aero-damping for the plunge mode component driven by twist motion induced perturbations (ζ_{TP}) is always negative.

In order to further examine the validity of the decomposed aero-damping, unsteady CFD flutter computations were carried out for the same geometry in the same flap mode with $\gamma = 0.5$. The flap mode used in this analysis is obtained from a linear superposition of the pure plunge and the pure twist modes studied (as illustrated in Figure 6). The aero-damping for the flap mode obtained directly from unsteady CFD solutions is plotted in Figure 7 as ζ_{FF} . As a comparison, the sum of the aero-damping contributions ζ_{PP} , ζ_{PT} , ζ_{TP} and ζ_{TT} obtained from work sum analysis is also shown in this plot. It is clearly seen that the two quantities are identical, even though calculated from solutions of completely different CFD computations. The same conclusion

FIGURE 8: Aerodynamic damping contributions for different mode shape parameter γ , $\theta_s = 45^\circ$.

is obtained by repeating this analysis at different flow conditions and for different blade stagger angles. This clearly demonstrates the validity of the aero-damping decomposition for blade vibrations in the flap mode shown in Equation 27. For the case studied here, the flap mode remains stable for all reduced frequencies, since the magnitude of the positive aero-damping ζ_{PP} is always higher than the magnitude of the negative aero-damping ζ_{TP} .

The observations are in agreement with the findings in [6] for a transonic fan blade vibrating in the 1F mode. The finding in this section is an important feature for blade flutter in the 1F mode, where the component of twist in the mode shape contributes to blade flutter stability (or instability) by perturbing the surrounding flow field, which interacts with the plunge motion to modify blade damping. It is worth noting that the observed trends regarding mode shape are independent of flow. It is also worth mentioning that mechanism observed here shows similarities with that in classical flutter theory for wings, where blade instability is triggered due to the coupling between bending and torsion modes.

Effect of twist component in a flap mode

Having demonstrated that aero-damping for a blade vibrating in any flap mode can be obtained through post-processing of the unsteady CFD solutions computed for pure plunge and pure twist modes, the parameter γ is subsequently varied to study the effect of twist component on blade flutter stability.

Figure 8 shows the comparison of calculated blade aero-damping for three flap modes with $\gamma = 0.5$, $\gamma = 0.7$ and $\gamma = 0.8$ respectively. It is noted that for clarity, the aero-damping contributions for the twist mode ζ_{PT} and ζ_{TT} remain negligible and are not shown in this plot. It can be seen from the plot that the aero-damping contribution ζ_{PP} is (quite obviously) independent of γ , whereas the aero-damping contribution ζ_{TP} remains negative and

its magnitude increases with the increase of γ . The negative aerodamping attributed to ζ_{TP} is more pronounced at low reduced frequencies, which results in a significant loss of stability in the flap mode ζ_{FF} . It can be seen that the stability for the flap mode with $\gamma = 0.7$ is reduced to critically stable at the reduced frequency of about 0.4, and the flap mode with $\gamma = 0.8$ becomes unstable for reduced frequencies below 1.4.

The analysis in this section clearly demonstrates the effect of mode shape on flutter stability of a vibrating blade. With the help of a simple work sum analysis, it is shown that, for blade vibration in zero inter-blade phase angle modes, the intrinsic aerodamping for the twist mode is an order of magnitude smaller than that for the plunge mode, and can usually be neglected in flutter assessment. This conclusion is likely to hold true for flow conditions away from stall or choke. The presence of flow separation and shock wave may lead to other interaction mechanisms where twist motion becomes dominant, however they are not the main focus of this work. The analysis also leads to an important finding that, in the absence of complex aerodynamic flow behaviours (such as flow separation), it is possible to make a blade flutter by merely increasing the amount of twist motion in a flap mode. Though from experience the amount of twist γ in a typical 1F mode for a rotor blade is usually less than 0.5, the magnitude of the negative aero-damping contribution ζ_{TP} in such cases can be significantly higher (such as the case shown in [6]), which results in negative overall damping for the flap mode.

It is worth noting that other parameters such as inter-blade phase angle, camber and mean loading can also be influential in determining blade flutter stability. However, their effects do not invalidate the trends observed here.

EFFECTS OF INCOMING ACOUSTIC GUST

In the next step, flutter stability of blades in the thin annulus blade row is investigated in the presence of an incoming acoustic gust. The purpose of the incoming gust is to mimic a reflected acoustic wave from bladed structure, ducting or intake. This is achieved by imposing perturbations of acoustic wave on a source plane at a distance away from the blade row. By doing so, the interaction between an incoming acoustic gust and the blade vibration can be investigated.

For all the cases studied here, the Mach number is maintained at $M = 0.3$. All vibration motions are fixed at a reduced frequency of 0.84. The amplitude of the gust is kept constant (representative of a reflected wave) and the phase is varied linearly between 0° and 360° . The frequency of imposed gust is the same as that of the blade vibration, so as to mimic the reflection of the outgoing acoustic waves generated by the vibration motion. For the studies performed here, upstream propagating acoustic gusts are imposed in the downstream field of the blades (studies with downstream propagating gusts yield similar conclusions and are thus not presented here). The imposed gust mimics

FIGURE 9: Axial variation of amplitude and phase of acoustic waves for *Case G*, 0° phase of incoming gust, $\theta_i = 45^\circ$, $f_r = 0.84$, pure plunge mode.

a reflected acoustic wave from downstream structure, e.g. blade row.

In order to isolate and analyse the effect of incoming acoustic gust on blade flutter stability, three series of cases were investigated in this work:

1. *Case V*: vibration of blades in the absence of incoming gust.
2. *Case VG*: vibration of blades in the presence of incoming gust.
3. *Case G*: imposing acoustic gust without blade vibration.

Findings based on *Case V* have been discussed in the previous section. The rest of this section focuses on the analysis of *Case VG* and *G* and the comparison with *Case V*. To gain more understanding of the unsteady flow field, method of wave-splitting [10] was adopted to decompose the perturbations into propagating waves.

Figure 9 shows an example of wave-split in the upstream and downstream fields of the blade. In this plot the amplitude and phase of acoustic pressure are plotted as a function of non-dimensional axial coordinate. The amplitude of unsteady pressure is normalised by the amplitude of the outgoing acous-

FIGURE 10: Blade forcing variation with phase of the incoming gust, $\theta_s = 45^\circ$, $f_r = 0.84$, pure plunge mode.

tic wave at the blade trailing edge in the absence of incoming gust. The phase is relative to blade motion at zero displacement and maximum positive velocity. The blade is situated between x/c_{ax} of -0.5 and 0.5 . It is seen from the amplitude plot that when the upstream propagating acoustic gust impinges on the blade row, part of it is transmitted through to the upstream field ($x/c_{ax} < -0.5$), and part of it is reflected and propagates back in the downstream direction ($x/c_{ax} > 0.5$). For the flow condition and stagger angle studied here, the amplitude of transmission coefficient (about 0.85) is much higher than that of reflection coefficient (about 0.1). These values are known to vary significantly when different blade geometries, flow conditions and modes are concerned [11].

In order to study the influence of incoming gust on vibration, blade forcing are calculated as the integration of forces over the surface. The amplitude and phase of forcing for *Case V*, *Case G* and *Case VG* are plotted in Figure 10 as a function of phase of the incoming gust. In these plots the amplitude is normalised by the amplitude in *Case V*. It can be seen that the forcing amplitude induced by the incoming gust alone (*Case G*) remains constant, and its phase varies linearly with respect to that of the incident wave. This is because the amplitude of the imposed gust is fixed and the only variable in this case is the phase of the imposed

FIGURE 11: Aero-damping variation with phase of the incoming gust, $f_r = 0.84$.

wave. Due to the presence of incoming acoustic gust, the forcing amplitude for a vibrating blade (*Case VG*) is seen to oscillate sinusoidally about the value in the absence of incoming gust (*Case V*). This deviation can be shown to be a function of the amplitude and phase of the imposed gust. Moreover, the blade forcing for *Case VG* shows good agreement with the complex summation of *Case V* and *Case G*. This indicates that for vibration in small amplitude, which is the case for flutter onset, the unsteady loading on the blade can be decomposed into contributions due to its vibratory motion and incoming gusts. In most situations, these two contributions are independent and can be evaluated separately.

Figure 11 shows the blade aero-damping, calculated using the energy method from the unsteady CFD solutions, as a function of phase of the incoming gust. In this figure, aero-damping of the blade with stagger angles of 0° , 30° , 45° and 80° are displayed using dashed curves for pure plunge vibration in *Case V*, solid curves for pure plunge vibration in *Case VG*, and dotted curves for pure twist vibration in *Case VG*. It is worth noting that, for clarity, the results for pure twist vibration *Case V* are not shown in this figure as its aero-damping remains small and does not vary significantly from *Case V* to *Case VG*. It can be seen from the plot that, as expected, the incoming acoustic gust affects the blade aero-damping for *Case VG* in a sinusoidal fashion. The deviation in blade aero-damping between *Case VG* and *Case V* cycles with a period of 360° phase of incoming gust, the exception being the 0° stagger case where the incident acoustic wave passes through the blade row unimpeded without inducing unsteady loading. With the increase of blade stagger, the effect of the incoming gust becomes more pronounced. Moreover, it is seen that the most detrimental gust phase varies as the stagger angle changes.

FIGURE 12: Blade forcing variation with phase of the incoming gust for *Case G*, $f_r = 0.84$, plunge motion.

The observed trends are further investigated by analysing the blade forcing variation due to the imposed acoustic gust alone. Figure 12 shows the amplitude and phase of blade forcing for *Case G* as a function of the phase of incoming gust. It is clearly seen that the incident acoustic gust induces zero unsteady loading on the 0° staggered blade. The amplitude of unsteady loading sees an increase with the increase of stagger angle. This can be explained as follows: as the blade stagger angle increases, the mode angle of the incident acoustic wave (plane wave at 0° with the engine axis) becomes more aligned with the direction of lift, which results in an increase in forcing amplitude. Moreover, a phase difference in blade forcing is seen between cases with different stagger angle. As the most destabilising condition occurs when the forcing is in phase with blade velocity (i.e. 0° phase of forcing), the most destabilising gust phase of 120° is expected for the cases of 30° and 45° stagger angles and gust phase of 210° for the case of 80° stagger angle. This effect is clearly visible in the computed aero-damping shown in Figure 11. Furthermore, it is also seen in Figure 11 that aero-damping of the blade for the pure twist mode ζ_{TT} is again an order of magnitude smaller than that for the pure plunge mode ζ_{PP} , indicating that the effect of the incoming acoustic gust is dominated by the interaction between the gust-induced unsteady lift and the plunge motion in blade vibration. This conclusion is likely to hold true for low inter-blade phase angle modes where the induced unsteady lift is dominant. It is however less accurate for large inter-blade phase angle modes where the effect of unsteady moment becomes more pronounced due to passage volume change.

Finally, the effect of incoming acoustic gust on flutter stability is investigated for blades vibrating in a flap mode. The analysis was conducted by performing flutter computations for the 45° stagger angle blade row in the *Case VG* setup, i.e. vibration with the presence of gust. It should be noted that, in this study, only the phase of incoming gust and the amount of twist in the flap mode γ are varied while fixing all other parameters. The obtained aero-damping values are plotted in Figure 13 as a function of the phase of incoming gust. Results are shown for three

FIGURE 13: Blade aero-damping for flap modes with different mode shape parameter γ in the presence of incoming acoustic gust, $\theta_s = 45^\circ$, $f_r = 0.84$.

flap modes: $\gamma = 0.5$, $\gamma = 0.7$ and $\gamma = 0.8$. The computed blade aero-damping in *Case VG* are compared with those obtained in *Case V*. It can be seen from the plot that the incoming gust can stabilise or destabilise the blade flutter stability depending on the phase of incoming gust. Moreover, the results in Figure 11 shows that the effect of incoming gust is dominated by the interaction between the incoming gust and the plunge motion. It is also seen from Figure 13 that the deviation in aero-damping due to incoming gust increases with the increase of twist in the mode shape. This can be understood by considering the work sum associated with the incoming gust.

For a blade vibrating in the flap mode whose motion is expressed using Equation 11, the aerodynamic work per cycle for the plunge mode component, due to unsteady loading induced by the incoming gust, w_{GP} , can be expressed as

$$w_{GP} = \int_{\mathcal{T}} \oint p_G \mathbf{n} \cdot (1 - \gamma) \mathbf{v}_p dS dt \quad (28)$$

where p_G denotes pressure perturbations induced by the gust.

Consequently, the ‘additional’ aero-damping induced by the incoming gust can be evaluated using

$$\zeta_{GP} = -\frac{1}{1 - \gamma} \frac{1}{v_{0p}^2} \int_{\mathcal{T}} \oint p_G \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{v}_p dS dt \quad (29)$$

It is seen from the above equation that, as the component of

twist γ increases, the influence of incoming gust on blade aero-damping grows.

Importantly, it is seen from Figure 13 that, the combined effect of having a substantial twist component in the mode shape and the presence of incoming acoustic gust can lead to flutter of an otherwise stable blade: stable $\gamma = 0.5$ Case V to unstable $\gamma = 0.7$ Case VG. This type of interaction has been demonstrated as one of the main causes of 1F mode flutter for fan blades and rotor blades embedded in multi-stage compressors [2–4, 11], where the lowest aerodynamic damping due to blade motion (flow and mode shape driven) and the most detrimental effect caused by acoustic reflection coincide.

CONCLUSION AND FURTHER WORK

The impact of mode shape and acoustic gust is assessed in this paper. With the help of work sum analysis of CFD solutions, contributions of blade aero-damping due to different unsteady loading sources are analysed individually.

It is shown that the aero-damping for the twist mode (ζ_{PT} and ζ_{TT}), driven by fluctuating moment, is an order of magnitude smaller than that for the plunge mode (ζ_{PP} and ζ_{TF}) which is driven by unsteady lift. For blade vibration in a flap mode, the component of twist motion contributes to the overall blade aero-damping by perturbing the surrounding flow field which interacts with the plunge vibration motion. The analysis also shows that, in the absence of flow separation, it is possible to make a blade flutter by merely increasing the amount of twist motion in a flap mode. Conversely, flutter mitigation is possible by reducing the amount of twist in the mode.

The effect of incoming acoustic gust on blade flutter stability is clearly demonstrated. The incident acoustic wave induces unsteady loading on the blade surface which in turn modifies the aerodynamic work and damping. This finding indicates that the aerodynamic damping contribution due to blade motion and incoming acoustic gust are also likely to be independent and can be analysed separately. Furthermore, the influence of incoming gust grows as the amount of twist in the mode shape increases. Importantly, it is clearly demonstrated, analytically and numerically, in this paper that, an otherwise stable blade can flutter due to the combined effects of mode shape and incoming gust.

The observations and conclusions obtained are by no means limited to the geometry and flow studied in this work. These aspects such as mode shape and acoustic reflection have been identified in recent works as key contributors for flutter in fans and rotors in multi-stage compressor. As turbomachinery blade aerofoils are thinned to improve performance and reduce weight, they are likely to remain as key aeroelastic challenges in designing a flutter-free machine.

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